
Research

The COVID-19 Crisis Reaction as a Catalyst for a Shift in Italy's Economic Status within the European Union

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Abstract: COVID-19 crisis presents an opportunity leading to Italy's rejuvenation and rehabilitation as a key EU member. Italy will receive 209 billion euros of the 750 billion euros allocated by the European Commission. They will be injected through the PNRR, allowing it to overcome structural challenges and addressing the main research questions: Does the coronavirus crisis response entail a shift in Italy's political and financial position within the European Union? The thesis uses a chronological and progressive method to allow a clear and detailed understanding and analysis of facts and data. Moreover, analyzing a country like Italy serves as a symptomatic model for so-called peripheral countries in the European Union. Differentiated Integration (DI) Theory is adopted in this study since it provides a systematic and relevant theoretical framework to analyze and assess the origins and effectiveness of the PNRR, which rest upon the concept of differentiation, and which will allocate resources based on the needs of each member state. I argue that the PNRR has all the necessary characteristics and requisites to allow Italy's economic rejuvenation and rehabilitation in the EU. It also supports the relevance of DI theory to analyzing and understanding the contemporary EU.

Keywords: Italy, COVID-19 recovery, financial status, Next Generation EU

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1. Introduction

The concept of a European Union was born in the legacy of the Second World War. The war left Europe shocked and saddened, with their economy in recession, massive civil and military losses, and a sense of political fatigue [9] (pp. 5-10). The purpose of an economic, social, and political Union of countries was to make the idea of a hypothetical conflict between them inconceivable and unfeasible [9] (p. 11). In the minds of the founding fathers, the European Union should have been first and foremost a Union of Principles, promoting humanitarian and progressive values to ensure that European citizens benefit from the never-ending global changes [19], followed by political and economic integration to regulate all aspects necessary for citizens' well-being.

The coronavirus pandemic initially undermined many of these basic assumptions. Former German Foreign Minister Joschka Fisher warned the European Union of the risk of the European dream failing due to the European abandonment of respect for diversity and the principle of solidarity since the policy pursued by Germany and the northern countries does not work for other countries like Italy. It is an austerity approach centered on limits rather than progress, which would lead to economic challenges and political and ideological concerns surrounding Europe's overall vision, and that showed its weaknesses and inability to face the pandemic with solidarity and coordination [56].

This research took Italy and Covid-19 within the context of the European Union as a case study, as analyzing a country like Italy serves as a symptomatic model for so-called peripheral countries in the European Union. Italy is a founding member historically at the core of the European project, nevertheless, it has lost its significance during the last many decades because of economic downturn and political turmoil, becoming a Southern or peripheral state. Indeed, at the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis, disparities, inequalities, and divisions thus widened between the so-called Northern and Southern countries, creating different perceptions and prescriptions for how the European Union should react and respond to the emergency.

Significantly, Italy grabbed the lead, positioning itself as the head of the Southern countries. It demanded the European Commission act to promote a more coordinated and collective EU response enabling all member states, according to their capabilities and situation, to effectively combat the pandemic and address the challenges of the pandemic recovery. In the end, France and Germany agreed on and proposed a historic recovery plan, the Next Generation EU (NGEU), of which Italy was a powerful advocate and on which it advised. For this project to succeed, member states must act as a genuine Union, overcoming differences and divisions to assist those member states most in need. This recovery plan and its implementation have initiated a transformation in the EU toward more differentiated integration with significant implications for member states and their citizens' economic, political, social, and emotional life.

Most importantly, this research addresses the potential opportunity that the COVID-19 crisis response represents for Italy to enhance its economic status within the European Union. This study is notable because it demonstrates the chronological order and advancement of facts. The main objective is to define a clear cause-and-effect relationship as understanding the main difficulties of the Italian economy and how these problems arose. EU countries came to the realization and the convergence in one coordinated and resilient policy, the NGEU, with Italy being its largest beneficiary, alone receiving 209 billion euros. As a result, if successfully executed, this strategy has the potential to restructure and revitalize the Italian economy, bringing it out of a condition of gridlock and stagnation.

2. Differentiated Integration Theory as a New Strategy for the EU

This research draws on the Differentiated Integration (DI) theory. Since the later 1990s, the European integration process has run along with the concept of differentiation. The DI theory designs a strategy or method for the reform and further development of the European Union, where international differentiation between member states, in terms of their preferences, needs, and speed, turns from deadlock into an advantage [46] (pp. 176-178). The success of diversified integration is dependent on the availability of realistic and mutually beneficial solutions for all diverse participants [46] (p. 176). Through the year, schools of thought described DI from different perspectives, notwithstanding the basic premise of integration that does not include all member states. In other words, certain member states integrate more than others, but the EU, as a whole, does not [53] (pp. 7-8).

Schimmelfennig points out how the orthodox IR theories of European integration have typically ignored the Union's increasingly diverse nature. They focus on bargaining talks to advance national and regional interests (intergovernmentalism theory), on the general institutional and transnational dynamics (neo-functionalism theory), as well as the constraining politics that has evolved because of globalization (post-functionalism theory) [47] (pp. 1172-1173). He highlights how despite the DI is inherent in every traditional thinking since the increasing integration led to widening preferences and capacities heterogeneity among member states. Yet, the incompatibility of national ambitions and structural and economic capabilities resulted in a fixed set of regulations based on unanimity consensus, which might eventually stymie further integration [47] (pp. 1173-1175).

Integration has always been considered a uniform process in which the EU rules are equally valid and apply to all member states. On the other hand, the DI is the product of uneven intergovernmental bargaining, allowing member states to engage in shared policies according to their capabilities and rhythm, presumably resulting in greater integration [46] (p.178). The latter is the most widely held perspective on differentiated integration among EU officials since it corresponds to the ambition to continue expanding EU integration while also broadening its membership. The premise underlying this differentiated vision is that each member state should be entitled to determine its level of engagement in the European project [53] (p.12).

The European Union is viewed through the lens of its challenge, which has revealed structural flaws and governance weaknesses, culminating in a political and existential quandary [10] (p.10). Even the Eurozone financial crisis, in which member countries effectively merged, emphasized the necessity for more distinction [48] (pp. 295-297). Although the single currency intended to promote economic and political integration, the reality was a collection of fragmented policies controlled by national governments, with member states coordinating their economy, fiscal and budgetary policies inequitably [22] (pp. 17-20). The EU governs by-laws and rules by numbers, disregarding or failing to build the reciprocal risk-sharing instruments essential for any fixed-currency zone to succeed [49]. Furthermore, the late-2000s

exogenous shock widened the divide between an export-led Northern Europe and a demand-led Southern Europe. Highly asymmetric intergovernmental bargaining began, favoring the stronger Northern creditor economies [10] (pp. 9-10).

Nonetheless, the more coordinated the member states, the more different interests among them came to light. The unified monetary policy and the scattered economic policies highlighted the problems of pursuing more straight regulations and conditionality norms vis-a-vis deeper cooperation [22] (pp. 17-20). The austerity and structural reforms led to disparities, inequalities, unemployment, and poverty rather than the expected convergence. The subsequent crises have lacked coordination and cohesion. Major divisions increased, not only vertically between north and south but also horizontally between west and east. Europe has never run at the same speed [22] (p. 26). It gave birth to an unequal interconnectedness between European countries, where some countries required more help and others less. Nevertheless, the rules continued to be uniform, not considering these disparities.

The DI theory proposes a way out of this impasse by allowing member states to collaborate and be more integrated into domains that suit their interests while excluding member states that reject integration and wish to maintain the status quo [46] (pp.178-180). Furthermore, in comparison to most orthodox theories, the DI theory helps us comprehend and explain the origins and design of the NGEU while proposing a new idea of integration that is more realistic to the political realities of the modern EU.

3. Background: Italy's Economic Status within the EU before the COVID-19 Pandemic

Italians and political parties attribute the poor development and near-stagnant economy to Eurozone fiscal austerity, conditionalities, and harsh limitations [8] (pp. 6-7). Since Italy is judged too large to fail and too big to bail, it is increasingly reliant on the European Central Bank (ECB) asset purchase program to support its public debt and it is subject to surveillance, austerity, and conditionality constraints imposed by other Eurozone members over time.

In the postwar period, the European Union was the means to rehabilitate and modernize Italy on the world stage, both economically, politically, and culturally [44] (pp. 927-928). In the wake of the signing of the Treaty of Rome, European integration contributed to solid income growth rates as Italian governments believed that the exogenous expansionary benefits of integration would extend from wealthier to poorer regions, resulting in a reduction in regional inequalities between North-South [38] (pp.25-26).

Italy experienced decades of rapid economic growth, with exports increasing from 20% to 36%, resulting in higher productivity and competitiveness, while, by the end of the 1990s, Italians began to spend their money abroad, increasing their reliance on exports and making it more difficult for the country to catch up to the Euro-4 economies of Belgium, France, Germany, and the Netherlands [51] (pp. 200-201). The Italian industry underwent a substantial reorganization, moving away from big-scale enterprises and toward a huge number of relatively small manufacturers [44] (pp. 931, 940-941).

Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) emerged in the 1970s to capitalize on the economies of scale afforded by European countries and new emerging economies such as China and India and were extremely suited and flexible to enable rapid and efficient changes in outlet markets in response to new demands [2] (pp. 6-10). However, SMEs had limitations as they were less productive, profitable, less inclined to invest, and less oriented toward R&D, with the result that banks were less willing to lend, creating a vicious circle. In addition, "familism" was very common, referring to the preference for poor managers loyal to the owner over competent managers who can increase corporate performance [33] (pp. 420-421).

Finally, after signing the Maastricht Treaty, the Italian economy started to collapse, causing a recession in 1992, which placed Italy's capacity to fulfil the requirements for membership of the EMU in question [51] (p. 200). Italy was not benefiting more from devaluing the currency and from the availability of internationally cheap and well-trained labor, thus founding itself a witness to the rise of interest rates and went down of heavily indebted firms [14] (pp. 767-768).

According to recent research, Italy profited the least from entering the EMU of all Member States (excluding Greece). Italy lacked the advantages of a globally spoken language like Britain did. Also, it lacked a robust currency used as a reserve currency, and its low exchange rate ranked with peripheral European nations such as Spain, Portugal, and Greece [44] (p.769).

Nevertheless, the Italian government has launched an ambitious fiscal reform, spending cuts, and tax collection program, dramatically reforming its economy according to the other European economies. The aim was to be part of the European Union economic convergence, which Italian politicians saw as an opportunity for economic growth and the first step toward further political integration [51] (pp. 201-202).

To join the EMU at any cost was a necessity due to the 120% national debt and the political incapability of Italian leaders to transform Italian bonds into coupons owned by Italians, who would have contributed to the nation's reconstruction

[14] (p. 770). As a result, the political class was replaced by politically neutral and technocratic leaders concerned with debt sustainability, anti-inflationary fiscal policy, privatization, public administration reform, and austerity [51] (p. 205). For the center-left government of Prodi (1996-2001) "entering Europe" were both the priority and a scapegoat to implement domestically otherwise difficult structural and political reforms [44] (p. 929).

During those years, Italy considered itself more aligned with the European Union as a whole, as a regional and cohesive bloc, but it also diverged from other member states' attitudes and methods of doing things, such as Germany [44] (pp. 929-930). During the Berlusconi administration, Italy's image of the Union turned to political contempt for Brussels bureaucrats, exacerbated by the rivalry between Italian Prime Minister Berlusconi and Italian President of the European Commission Prodi.

Quaglia and Radelli underline how, in the early 2000s, support for European integration declined, with ministers openly Eurosceptic for the first time in postwar Italy [44] (pp. 930-932). Italy began a momentum of negligence and ignorance towards the EU influence, especially on domestic policies such as reduction of taxes, an increase of minimum pensions, constructions of large-scale infrastructures, and fiscal policy, also by temporally exceeding the ceiling set by the Stability and Growth Pact. The country attempted to reform and reduced the pressure imposed by the Union, especially on the financial aspect and public debt, but this turned out unsuccessful due to other member states' reticence [44] (pp. 932, 937).

The EMU policy framework triggered a process of competition between national economic systems, adding to the already fragile Italian financial situation and classifying it among the lowest in the Eurozone concerning growth rates and competitiveness measures [14] (pp. 766-770). Because of non-standard employees and job instability, the training necessary to meet the changing skills required in the labor market, poverty risks, and income inequalities have expanded. Simultaneously, long-term care needs for the elderly increased because of changing demographics, emphasizing the importance of labor reforms and contract standardization. The idea was to improve entrance flexibility and attract companies to sign open-ended and fixed-term contracts. Nonetheless, it led to unstable relationships between workers and employees: the former spent less time and money on employee training leading to a drop in job quality and productivity [33] (pp. 425-430). The Berlusconi government was responsible for an unsuccessful reduction of the primary budget surplus, which inevitably led to borrowing requirements from the EU and, consequentially, to an increase in public expenditures and the downfall of public revenues to reduce fiscal pressure [14] (pp. 770-772).

Economy discipline and fiscal stabilization, with significant primary budget surpluses, were the top priorities following the Berlusconi government, particularly during the European debt crisis, where a sense of disengagement and neglect dominated Italian-EU relations [44] (p. 939). The conventional wisdom held that public spending needed cuts to reduce the national debt. However, this is only true in the short run because consistent public spending lessens the severity of the recession, while public investments and expenditures, such as education, health, research, and infrastructure, encourage growth in the long run [32] (p. 15).

The economy and the quality of life weakened; school quality deteriorated; the time it takes to seek justice in civil and administrative courts increased, and rising signs of fragility in large private-sector businesses joined the weakening of state enterprises [52] (pp. 24-26). These forces trap the nation in a state of irreversible stagnation, marked by the impoverishment of the productive matrix of the Italian economy and the quality of its trade flows.

Approximately 60% of the downturn in Italy's growth output can therefore be directly attributed to Italy's self-imposed adherence to EMU requirements and the 2008-09 financial crisis [51] (p. 222). Although the ECB had been slow to respond to the crisis, former president Mario Draghi famously stated in 2012 that he would do "whatever it takes to save the euro," including potentially unlimited purchases of distressed bonds. These purchases aimed to avoid a period of too-low inflation [39] (p. 22) and a potential collapse of debt, accumulated particularly by northern banks exposed in southern sovereigns [41] (pp. 196-202). Italy managed to reach a balanced budget in 2013 through severe austerity measures worth 45.5 billion euros overall. But, years of corruption, distrust, political instability, and incapacity, left investors still reticent in trusting Italian financial markets. Germany alone reduced its net exposure to the Italian debt by 88%, from 8 billion to less than 1 [45] (p. 82).

Finally, quantitative easing measures were allowed in 2015, with the program aiming to purchase each country's capital key (17.5 percent for Italy). Furthermore, each issuer, such as the Italian State, was limited to 33 percent of the total amount of each issuance, with a maximum of 50 percent of each country's debt issued [41] (p. 203). The ECB's substantial measures and the significant expansionary stimulus provided allowed for the revival of domestic demand and, as a result, the accumulation of productive capital [3] (p. 6). In 2016, the ECB introduced a series of TLTROs to stimulate aggregate demand by providing incentives to banks to lend to non-financial corporations and households [39] (p. 22). Interest rates continued to be progressively reduced, reaching 0 in 2016, and the overnight deposit rate was raised to -0.40 in 2016-2017, with the latter applied to the TLTROs [34] (pp. 64-69).

Still, in 2016 GDP growth was only 0,9%, but for the first time since 2007, the recovery of investor confidence has favored the recovery of accumulation, allowing growth in the profitability of businesses. This was accompanied by a drop in interest rates, which helped reducing financial vulnerability indicators and keep financing demands under check [3] (pp. 3-5). Even so, in 2018, the Italian GDP had still not recovered to its 2007 level. The dignity decree of 2018 resulted in a minor increase and growth in employment, continuing a trend that began in 2017, with the unemployment rate falling from 11.2 percent to 10.6 percent. Above all, permanent employment has increased because of the implementation of contribution relief for young people under 35 years old and new temporary job restrictions in the final months of the year. The latter benefitted new employees, but it diminished the chance of individuals currently on a fixed-term contract remaining in employment when the contract expires [4] (pp. 4-7).

The economy began to tremble again in 2018, with only a 0.3 percent growth rate in 2019 [5] (p. 4), due to a national bond upheaval and uncertainty surrounding a new government, and tensions in the securities market quickly rose [16] (pp. 5-6). Foreign investors began to sell off substantial amounts of Italian assets, influenced by the rising spread between Italy and Germany, which rose to 330 points only in mid-November [16] (pp. 5-6). The League-Five Star Movement administration in power from June 2018 until August 2019 aimed to modify or abolish the EU balanced-budget provision to implement effective anti-cyclical measures [40] (pp. 356-358). The idea was to provide more flexibility for action, but it was never implemented because breaking this EU budgetary regulation would have resulted in a negative reaction from foreign and private investors, because fiscal stimuli financed primarily through domestic borrowing would have meant higher interest rates and possibly contractionary policies [24] (p. 38). The European Commission intended to keep the budget financially neutral without providing fiscal stimulants. The assumption was that delivering fiscal stimuli now would have meant going against the Stability and Growth Pact and the EMU macroeconomic framework to keep markets quiet [51] (p. 197). Against this backdrop, tensions have eased since early 2019, owing to an agreement between the Italian Government and the European Commission regarding Italy's fiscal policies, the easing of monetary conditions in the eurozone, and the improvement in global financial market conditions [16] (pp. 6-7).

On the verge of the COVID-19 socio-economic crisis, Italy found itself with long-term structural problems since the end of the 1990s, both internally and externally. According to Cottarelli and Marelli, and Signorelli, it is unthinkable to restore the Italian economy without facing such structural problems as: the long neglect and less diffusion of new technologies, the contained expenses in R&D, the low competitiveness, the industrial structure too unbalanced; and also, the relatively low level of human capital and the progressive aging of the population, the obsolete model of specialization [13] (pp. 5-7), the widespread phenomena of corruption and tax evasion, the slow and inefficient bureaucracy, in addition with the organized crime and the uncertainty of the justice system [33] (pp. 411-415). Another reason for the Italian inability to swim out of the recession is the fiscal strategy adopted by the politicians, especially the later Five Star Movement, which Storm defines as a "one-leg" fiscal stimuli policy. In fact, it aims to revive domestic demand by increasing public spending without considering the long-run spillover effects [51] (pp. 232-233). According to Schimelfennig, this was a logical consequence of the increasing liberal intergovernmentalism that developed among the states since integration and the diversity of choices and capacities grew.

To summarize the widening heterogeneity among member states resulted in the division between net contributor and net recipient or between debtor and creditor [47] (pp. 1176-1177). As a result, Italy sought protection from outside competitive pressures, asking for more flexibility, adaptation, and differentiated integration according to states' different needs and paces, while net contributors to the EU budget opposed any relaxation and extension of EU subsidies [47] (pp. 1176-1177).

Furthermore, the inability to keep up with the other member countries stemmed from its own central administrative and political shortcomings, requiring the Troika to impose stringent and austere restrictions to meet EU criteria and giving the impression of an Italy asking for assistance and supervision.

4. Discussion: Italy's Recovery Plan: A Boost in the Economy?

4.1 The National Plan of Recovery and Resilience (PNRR):

The National Plan of Recovery and Resilience (PNRR) is a document that each member state must develop to receive Next Generation EU (NGEU) funding [11]. Between 1999 and 2019, the GDP in Italy only grew by a total sum of 7.9%, less than 0.5% each year. In the same period in Germany, France, and Spain, increased, respectively, by 30.2, 32.4, and 43.6 percent. Between 2005 and 2019, the proportion of the population living in absolute poverty increased from 3.3 percent to 7.7 percent before peaking at 9.4 percent in 2020 [12] (p. 2).

The NGEU, therefore, represents an opportunity for the country to resume a sustainable and lasting economic growth path by removing the obstacles that have blocked Italian growth in recent decades. On 25th April 2021, the Draghi government sent the text of the PNRR to Parliament, following the recommendations of European institutions and various local authorities, political forces, and social partners, all of which are integral components of the Italian economy and politics [11]. The PNRR was eventually, approved by the European Commission on 22 June 2021 and by the EU Economy and Finance Council (ECOFIN) on July 13, 2021 [1].

The PNRR which allocates through reforms and investments of 191.5 billion euros, is structured in full coherence with the six pillars of the NGEU and largely satisfies the parameters set by the European regulations on quotas for green and digital projects. Following these cornerstones, the precise Missions and components of each plan will be produced, as for Italy with 16 Components organized into six Missions [12] (p. 4).

The first pillar focuses on the green transition. The first pillar focuses on the green transition, it is directly related to the European Green Deal proposed in 2019 by European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen, with the EU's combined objective of attaining climate neutrality by 2050 and lowering greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 [18]. In this regard, the NGEU regulation provides that at least 37% of planned investment and reform expenditure in the PNRR must support climate objectives [27]. Furthermore, all investments and reforms contemplated by these plans must adhere to the premise of causing no extensive environmental harm [43]. Developing advanced digital technologies is necessary for the protection of water and marine resources, the transition to a circular economy, the reduction, and recycling of waste, the prevention of pollution, and the restoration of healthy ecosystems, such as forests, coastal areas, etc.

Italy is among the countries most at risk for climate change, according to the Climate Change Quality Index 2020 study delivered in Madrid during the Cop25 and produced by Germanwatch, CAN, and NewClimate Institute, with the cooperation of Legambiente for Italy [55]. In the IPCC survey, over 50 thousand people died from more than 12 thousand adverse weather incidents from 1999 to 2018 [15]. In this statistic, Italy ranks 26th globally for climate change vulnerability and 6th for climate change-related deaths [28]. As a result, the ecological transition can play an important role in increasing the competitiveness of the production system, encouraging the start-up of new and high-value-added entrepreneurial activities, and favoring the creation of stable employment, while also leaving a greener country and a more sustainable economy for future generations [12] (p. 16).

The digital pillar is the second keystone of every plan, to which it must invest at least 20% of its entire budget [27]. According to the most recent version of the DESI index, Italy has competitiveness and technical development deficit that dates to the late 1990s; Italy ranks 24th among the 27 European Union member states in terms of technological innovation [12] (p. 16). Therefore, closing this gap and promoting investments in technologies, infrastructures, and digital processes are essential to improve Italian and European competitiveness and market adaptability [12] (pp. 10-20). The objective of the PNRR is to rationalize and digitalize public administration and the development of digital public services. Connectivity must also be increased, especially by expanding the usage of very high-capacity telecommunications networks (TLC). The costs for users must be sustainable, and the speed of network creation must increase using new technologies such as 5G, Fiber, FWA, etc. [12] (pp. 12, 186). Imperative is for the government and SMEs, to invest in R&D so that citizens' digital skills and access to them, are developed and improved [12] (pp. 10-12).

Following the European Annual Sustainable Growth Strategy 2021, the third pillar calls on each member country to build a more robust and inclusive economy based on equal opportunities, fair working conditions, protection, and social inclusion [43]. The fourth pillar is social and territorial cohesion. Each member country must strengthen cohesion and reduce disparities between local, regional, and urban centers and rural areas. Female empowerment and the fight against gender discrimination, the growth of skills, abilities, and employment prospects of young people, territorial rebalancing, and the development of the South, are pursued as transversal objectives in all components of the PNRR. It should be noted, for example, that about 40% of the territorializable resources of the Plan are destined for Southern Italy, reflecting the attention paid to the issue of territorial rebalancing [27].

The last fundamental pillars concern the health and education of new generations and young people. The pandemic highlighted the vulnerability and other structural weaknesses of health care systems, and the need to create policies for the new generations so that they will not suffer permanent damage from the COVID-19 crisis [43].

The PNRR is divided, as aforementioned, into six Missions. The first Mission "innovation, digitalization, competitiveness, culture, and tourism" allocates 40.29 billion from the Recovery and Relief Facility (RRF) (21.04% of the PNRR) and 8.74 billion from the Complementary Plan [27]. One of the aims of the first mission is to cover the entire territory with ultra-broadband networks by 2026, ensuring 100% coverage of Italian families and companies [35]. Further aims include improving the competitiveness of industrial chains and facilitating the internationalization of businesses. It also invests in two sectors that characterize Italy: tourism and culture [12] (pp. 34, 36, 38, 41, 83-84, 114). Accordant to the Ministry

of Innovation and Digital Transition, a digital transition could occur only by closing the digital skills gap, with at least 70% of the population digitally proficient, spreading digital identification and guaranteeing that 70% of the population uses it; and lastly innovate by 2026 at least 75% of Italian PAs on board using cloud services; At least 80% of vital government services should be available online [35].

The Second Mission “green revolution and ecological transition” allocates 59.46 billion from the RRF (31.05 % of the PNRR) and 9.16 billion from the Complementary Plan. This Mission aims at achieving the green and ecological transition of society and the economy to make the system sustainable and ensure its competitiveness [27]. The interventions also include investments in more sustainable agriculture, a more circular economy, increased renewable energy consumption, and improved waste management capacity, as well as investments in the establishment of more sustainable mobility and industrial chains. It also provides for actions to improve the efficiency of public and private real estate assets; initiatives to combat hydrogeological instability, safeguard and promote the biodiversity of the area, and ensure the security of supply and sustainable and efficient management of water resources [12] (pp. 34-38, 41, 116-117, 152).

The third mission “infrastructure for sustainable mobility” allocates 25.40 billion from the RRF (13.26% of the PNRR) and 6.06 billion from the Complementary Plan, aiming at investing in more ecological mobility, such as the railway nexus, creating more sustainable mobility, with particular attention to the South [27]. In 2019, Italy had the rail share of total freight transport, 11.9%, lower than the EU average, 17.6% [12] (p. 19). This Mission promotes the optimization and digitalization of air traffic and aims to ensure the interoperability of the national logistics platform NLP for the port network [12] (pp. 19, 38, 41, 154).

The fourth Mission “education and research” allocates 30.88 billion from the RRF (16.13% of the PNRR) and 1 billion from the Complementary Plan [27]. This focuses on creating a more effective system, for accompanying young people in their training path, allowing them to enter the labor market in harmony with their abilities and efficiency. Thus, the goal is to close structural, quantitative, and qualitative deficiencies in the supply of education services throughout the educational cycle [12] (pp. 34, 36-38, 41, 83-84, 171). It increases kindergarten spots, improves university access, develops guiding tools, and reforms teacher recruitment and training. It also includes a significant strengthening of basic and applied research systems and new tools for a technology turnover to raise growth potential [12] (pp. 34, 36-38, 41, 83-84, 171).

The fifth Mission “cohesion and inclusion” allocates 19.85 billion from the RRF (10.37% of the PNRR) and 2.77 billion from the Complementary plan, focusing on better territorial cohesion and inclusion [27]. It intends to invest in social infrastructure, develops active labor policies, and promote women’s dual and entrepreneurial systems. It improves the protection system for situations of social and economic fragility, families, and parenthood [12] (pp. 26, 34, 36-38, 40-41, 198). Hence, it promotes the role of sport as an inclusion factor. Specific attention is paid to territorial cohesion, strengthening the Special Economic Zones, and the national strategy of inland areas. It enhances the Universal Civil Service and promotes the role of the third sector in public policies [12] (pp. 38, 68, 216). This Mission perfectly implements the Country Specific Recommendations (CSR) 2 of 2019, which asked to intensify the efforts to counteract the hidden policies; ensure that active labor market policies and social policies are effectively integrated and involve especially young people and vulnerable groups [20]. Important in this regard was the introduction by the former Conte Government of the Citizenship Basic Income, which means, the introduction of a universal income scheme [36].

Finally, the sixth and final Mission focuses on health, an area exposed to cuts and decreases in funding, with 15.63 billion allocated from the RRF (8.16 percent of the PNRR) and 2.89 billion from the Complementary Plan [27]. This Mission concerns three main objectives: the strengthening of prevention and assistance in the area, the integration of health and social services, and the modernization of the technological equipment of the National Health Service, such as the Electronic Health Record, and the development of telemedicine. It fosters scientific research in the biomedical and health sectors, as well as the advancement of health system personnel's technical, digital, and management abilities [12] (pp. 37, 39-42, 222).

The main turning point in the PNRR is the emphasis on reforms, including the reform of public administration, the judicial system through the simplicity and rationalization of laws, and reforms to promote competition [23]. The reforms are accompanied by a substantial relaunch of investments, after years of moderate budget consolidation. Reforms and investments will help boost total factor productivity and with it the potential growth of the Italian economy. The availability of a considerable number of subsidies through the NGEU instruments provides a significant boost in the accumulation of public and private capital and innovation while minimizing the impact on the deficit and public debt [12] (p. 24). It is also critical to highlight how the PNRR complies with the Country Specific Recommendations (CSR) for 2019 and 2020. Fundamental for the Commission was and still is to reduce the tax burden on labor, through tax concessions, cadastral reforms, as well as the fight against tax evasion, to non-invoicing, with the consequent increase in the

use of electronic payments [20]. Emphasis is also placed on the pension reforms that must be implemented fully to reduce the weight of old-age pensions in public spending and create margins for other social and public spending that are conducive to growth [20]. Nonetheless, the latter outcome is the most difficult to agree on since the Budget Law 2022 would involve new negotiations and restrictions, including a probable return to the Fornero Law [54]. However, in 2020, the so-called tax wedge on employees decreased, increasing the monthly bonus for employees from 80 to 100 euros. The 2021 Budget Law also made this measure permanent. New social contributions, particularly in the south, have been allocated, in addition to the zeroing of contributions paid by employers when hiring women or young people under 35 [12] (p. 26). The fight against tax evasion continues, also through the promotion and dissemination of electronic payments, promoted with the "Italia Cashless" plan, which aims to reduce the maximum limit on the use of cash to 1,000 euros from January 2022 [12] (p. 26).

To enable the PNRR wide dissemination Italian Government created a specialized portal called Italia Domani to allow individuals to actively engage through clear, efficient, and accessible communication on the measures, investments, reforms, and their benefits to Italy [27]. The portal builds on four concepts: transparency, simplicity, immediacy, and personalization. The dynamic component will also be critical in meeting the requirement to keep the ever-changing audience informed, both in terms of editorial creation and data exchange [12] (pp. 241-242). Finally, the organizational model proposed for the implementation of the Italian PNRR aims to promote synergy and complementarity between development and territorial cohesion actions and interventions, while also adhering to the fundamental principles of EU policies: the principle of subsidiarity, the principle of proportionality, partnership, participation, policy coherence, budgetary synergies, and strengthening institutional capacity and policy learning between institutions [12] (p. 241).

The pandemic highlighted and exacerbated structural problems inherent in the economy and organization of the country. Politicians, more than ever, have demonstrated a collective desire to tackle these challenges, despite the hurdles that lie ahead. The reforms that the administration proposes to adopt will thus be the turning point of the PNRR, addressing the country's structural weaknesses, such as persistent regional, intergenerational, and gender disparities that inhibit economic development and growth potential [21].

Three measures aim to achieve this goal: horizontal reforms, enabling reforms, and sectoral reforms. Horizontal, or context, reforms attempt to improve the country's economic efficiency, competitiveness, and equity. Carlo Cottarelli believes that public administration and the judicial system must be changed fast for the nation to function more efficiently and effectively [13] (pp. 5-7). Secondly, sectoral reforms are envisaged within every Mission and concern innovative regulations related to specific economic activities and interventions [27]. These intend to implement more efficient regulatory and procedural regimes in each sectoral field, resulting in a more resilient, green, digitalized, and efficient country [27]. Finally, enabling reforms to aim to create a smoother and quicker system, dialogue, and cooperation between the State, public, and private actors [27].

4.2 Horizontal Reforms: Public Administration Reform and Judicial System Reform:

The weak administrative capacity of the Italian public sector has long represented an obstacle to the improvement of the services offered and to public investments [12] (pp. 45-46), both because of weaknesses in the administrative structure, and in the approach of individuals to the state and the administration itself [13] (pp. 61, 69-71). In Italy, there is too much bureaucracy, which is slow and not transparent [13] (pp. 69-72). According to a study conducted by Cer-Rete Imprese Italia, reducing bureaucratic costs by about 25%, especially for SMEs, would result in a GDP higher of 1% after four years [13] (pp. 71-72).

Since a corrupt economy not only performs poorly but distorts public spending and damages the competition mechanism, simplifying the bureaucracy and improving its performance make tax evasion and corruption more difficult [13] (pp. 45-50). Over the last decade, the number of PA employees decreased, while those still working have an average age of 50. An older workforce combined with a changing economic and production model leads to a mismatch in skills available and skills needed [12] (pp. 44-45).

The reform of the PA has long been one of the European Commission's priorities, as expressed in both the 2019 and 2020 CSR [21]. The European Commission pointed out the necessity to improve the effectiveness of PA, investing in the skills of public employees, accelerating digitalization, and increasing the efficiency and quality of local public services [20].

Based on these recommendations and the need to ensure the correct advancement of the PNRR, the Government has outlined a program of reforms and investments based on four main axes: Access, Good Administration, Skills, and Digitalization.

To create better Access, it is necessary to streamline and make the selection procedures more effective as well as promote generational change. The recruitment procedure is still slow evidenced by waiting times of up to four years for candidates taking civil service examinations to become hired. In addition to slowness, these procedures do not consider individual technical skills and aptitudes, which makes PA less attractive for young talents [12] (pp. 45-46). Also, the PNRR envisaged the creation of a new portal, inPA, whose purpose is to connect supply and demand inquiries in the public sector and to provide a varied range of opportunities for work with permanent employment, with a focus on geographic criteria, abilities, and specialization [26].

Good Administration aims to simplify rules and procedures. The European Commission estimates that thanks to this, member states can save 5 billion euros every year [35]. The intended result is to create a complete, uniform, and updated catalog of all procedures and related regimes, with full legal validity throughout the national territory, to reduce time and costs for citizens and businesses. Moreover, through the "once-only" principle the PA aims to improve intervention monitoring and information and data communication between the various levels of the PA and between the PA and citizens, to ensure greater transparency and credibility [12] (pp. 47-49).

The purpose of Skills is to align knowledge and organizational skills to the new needs of the job market and of an innovative administration. Therefore, it is vital to strengthen human resource strategic planning along with improving and constructing coherent and varied training and career routes based on individual aptitudes and talents [12] (pp. 49-50). The PNRR intends to bring greater mobility and alternation within the PA, both nationally and internationally, allowing for the promotion of the worthiest and a more open, honest, cooperative, and smooth structure [12] (pp. 49-50).

Lastly, Digitalization is a transversal tool to better realize the previous axes [12] (pp. 45-50). The aim is to allow the simplification, speeding up, and efficiency of the PA, also increasing its transparency and credibility toward citizens and businesses [12] (pp. 50-51). In the end, improving the administrative capacity is a pre-condition for the effective delivery of public investment and the use of EU funds, with positive spillovers on private investment and GDP growth [20]. The European Commission many times pointed out in the CSR of 2019 and 2020 how Italy needed to reform the judicial system to increase efficiency, and reduce corruption, to develop better the economy of the country [20]. Feeble justice affects the financial circumstances of families and enterprises since lengthier processes relate to poorer participation of firms in global value chains and lower firm size [12] (p. 52). The International Monetary Fund identified several reasons (all prevalent in Italy) why the delay of justice harms growth. For starters, international investors favor nations where the rule of law is most effective. Second, enterprises are smaller in nations with dysfunctional judicial systems. Third, countries with well-functioning judicial systems develop more export advanced technology and products. Finally, banks lend more easily in countries where the legal system moves quickly.

Traditionally, there are three main reasons for delayed bureaucracy. The first is a lack of appropriate investment resources. Although, this is not the situation in Italy, which, according to the European Commission Cepej 2014 report, spent roughly 8 billion euros on justice, or 0.5% of GDP, much as Germany and more than France [13] (p. 85). The second reason is resource mismanagement, which is observed in the Italian court system. Indeed, the state's earnings from civil lawsuit payouts were among the lowest in Europe. Furthermore, until a few years ago, the payment of attorneys was decided by professional rates based on the number of activities performed, which may have encouraged the prolongation of the processes. Finally, the third factor is discernible in the increase in the number of requests for trials because of the growth in the index of litigation [13] (pp. 85-88). Thus, investors, people, and foreign observers demanded greater speed and clarity in judicial decisions [12] (pp. 52-53). It is necessary to reform both the procedure process and the organizational structure, to minimize the large backlog that burdens the court offices.

To achieve effective and efficient justice the PNRR must achieve reforms on the organizational level, in the extra-procedural dimension, and in the endo-procedural dimension, which are all complementary to one another. The guidelines' main goal is to: 1) bring the process office to full implementation; 2) develop the system's administrative capacity, enhancing human resources while also ensuring the contribution of technical professionalism and organizational innovation; 3) increase the degree of digitalization of justice through further enhancement of the telematic process and the use of advanced knowledge tools; 4) ensure efficient and modern building standards; 5) finally, to establish the groundwork

for a genuine anti-recidivism campaign that prioritizes re-education and social integration of inmates in the penal system [12] (pp. 51-53).

The Justice Reform is taking shape in several key intervention areas: 1) organizational interventions: trial office and administration strengthening. The goal is to simplify forms, simplify procedural models, shorten timeframes, and promote the efficacy and collaboration of judges and parties; 2) civil trial reform and alternative dispute settlement; 3) tax justice reform; 4) criminal trial reform [12] (pp. 57-58). An excessive length of the process damages both the guarantees of the persons involved and the interest of the legal system in the assessment and the persecution of crimes, making the state machinery slower [20].

It is necessary to speed up the times thanks to the simplification of acts and notifications for crimes, more swiftly collecting evidence, the possibility of resorting to alternative rites, a smooth and faster first-degree debate [12] (pp. 60-61); 5) and judicial system reform [27]. It is necessary to improve the management of resources, the organization of judicial activity, and guarantee autonomy for the judiciary based on the constitutional values of good performance and the impartiality of the jurisdiction. Finally, it is necessary to reduce the length of proceedings and the time needed to become a judge [27].

4.3 Enabling Reforms: Simplification and Competition:

The simplification of law is a critical reform intervention that supports all six Missions and promotes the country's prosperity [27]. The primary factor is the gradual depletion of financial, human, and instrumental resources, which has reduced the PA's administrative competence. Secondly, organizational reforms did not follow legislative measures simplification. The PNRR, therefore, aims to simplify the legislation, acting on the organization and digitalization of the PA [12] (p. 64).

The simplification of laws will accrue to society and the economy because of sophisticated technology and artificial intelligence. Moreover, a more accurate, manageable, appropriate, and efficient set of standards will also be more under the EU concept of clarity, comprehensibility, and accessibility [12] (pp. 64-65). It is essential to simplify laws in areas of critical competitiveness and growth, such as public contracts, the environment, investments – particularly in the South –, corruption, and digitalization [27]. Cottarelli pointed out how too many and too complex regulations can fuel corruption and disrupt the economy, sometimes also due to those laws created to fight it in the first place [13] (pp. 52-55). As a result, the implementation of a platform for better cooperation and transparency among the government and the public administration will reduce both state and administration costs by creating a single access point to public information, simplifying, and speeding up the process of acquiring and sharing data and information, and lowering corruption risks [12] (pp. 64-65).

The PNRR aims to reduce and rationalize the rules for public procurement and concessions, implement European regulations, reduce the documentary and economic burdens on the subjects who participate in public procedures, to relaunch public activity [12] (pp. 65-68).

A second simplification, closely tight to the building and public activities, regards the environments. As a matter of fact, despite the necessity for a rejuvenation of the economy, it is fundamental to develop and boost progress considering their environmental impact [27]. The PNRR intends to expand and strengthen the Ministry of Ecological Transition's capacity, clarify existing legislation, create faster and more simplified procedures, and incentivize public procurement contracts in each territory. Finally, a specific body concerning the environmental impact assessment (VIA) will monitor the works envisaged by the PNRR [12] (p. 67). Another fundamental norm simplification is regarding investment in the South. As aforementioned, the gap between the Northern and Southern regions is one of the complex Italian weaknesses. Even though the PNRR handles 40% of the financial resources for the South's modernization and development, resources must run concurrently with the simplification of norms and regulations for enterprises based in the South to incentivize jobs and reduce unemployment [37].

The promotion and protection of fair competition are milestones of the European Union system. Competition links to economic growth, so promoting more transparent competition is necessary for the recovery and development of the post-pandemic economy [27].

The major rules, created from scratch in the system, are five and cover both structural and organizational domains. First, the telecommunications sector, the port sector, and the electricity networks will create strategic infrastructures to guarantee better communication via ultra-broadband, finalize transparent and firm criteria for the issue of concessions, and therefore their more efficient operation. A second intervention concerns the removal of barriers to entry into the markets, making it necessary to overcome some regulatory obstacles to the free development of economic activities [12] (pp.

75-77). Reference focus on the concessions of large hydroelectric derivation, distribution of natural gas, motorway concessions, and the sale of electricity underlining the importance of transparency and efficiency, not only to improve competition itself but to also guarantee consumers greater certainty [12] (p. 76).

In the field of public services, it is necessary to promote rationalization of the legislation, with the adoption of a single text that ensures a more responsible appeal by the administrations, under the general principle of proportionality of the duration of public service contracts [27]. In the healthcare system, more transparent approaches and standards must be introduced. Finally, better environmental sustainability will be required, such as improved waste management efficiency or the installation of charge stations for electric vehicles. A fourth rule provides for the amendment of the current antitrust legislation. The goal is to introduce regulatory changes to ensure greater consistency of the national framework with that of the Commission and EU countries and to evaluate antitrust enhancement tools to counter the economic power of companies operating in multiple markets [12] (p. 77). In conclusion, the reform provides for the introduction of rules necessary for the implementation of the current regulation, intending to consolidate, simplify, and digitalize the surveillance system.

4.4 Sectoral Reforms:

These reforms contribute to achieving the objectives of social equity and improving the competitiveness of the production system [CSC 2019]. Tax reform is among the key actions to respond to the country's structural weaknesses. Indeed, throughout the years emerged an articulated and intricate tax structure, which has frequently served as an impediment and a brake on national and foreign investments.

The PNRR intends to collect and rationalize tax legislation in a single text, the rules of which have stability over time, and that allows for the simplification of the system and the implementation of legal certainty. In this light, a reform of the IRPEF is conceivable to gradually lower the tax burden, encourage tax compliance, and increase the involvement of women and young people in the labor market [12] (p. 78). A second pivotal reform is the Family Act, which contains measures to support families and children, promote women's participation in work, and support young people. It aims to create a single and universal allowance, strengthen the welfare system, and active policies aimed at female and youth employment [27]. This single stipend will be distributed to households following ISEE guidelines and under universality and progressivity criteria. In addition to the single allowance, the Family Act asks for the reorganization of educational assistance measures for children and the introduction of supplementary social security to fulfill and ensure more justice and harmony between work and family life. Finally, the Family Act includes provisions to assist young people in gaining financial independence and emancipation [12] (pp. 78-80). Finally, a third major reform focuses on workers' income support, to build a more egalitarian, sustainable system of shock absorbers capable of coping with changes as well as labor market insecurity by assisting with employment transitions and lessening the social impact of the crisis [12] (pp. 80-81). Income support will link with active and training policies to maximize the employability of workers and their rapid relocation to the labor market [27].

5. Conclusions

The PNRR, created in reaction to the COVID-19 crisis, devised a way to address Italy's economic, and structural challenges. The historical background of the Italian economic role frames Italy within the European Union, underlying the difficulties that arose because of the unequal intergovernmental relations among member states and the increasing external pressures imposed by European institutions. It is possible to hypothesize two different paths for Italy based on whether the outcomes will have positive or negative consequences. If the PNRR's measures will be effectively, efficiently, and correctly executed, the country's economic, political, and social situation will have positive outcomes and spillover. The RRF alone accounts for 9.5 percent of GDP, with an extra 30 billion (1.5 percent of GDP) supplied through an additional budget variance, bringing the whole effort that Italy expects to continue to about 11 percent of nominal GDP. As a result, if appropriately applied, the Draghi administration forecasts that GDP will have increased by 3.6 percent in 2026, the year of the PNRR's conclusion. Italy expects a GDP growth of 3.8 percent in 2022, 2.5 percent in 2023, and 1.7 percent in 2024 on an annual basis. Because of growing energy costs, inflation would be 3.5 percent in 2022 and 1.6 percent on average during the two years 2023-24 [6]. In addition, higher spending for the design and implementation of public projects will impact the demand, as will higher investments, which will increase the stock of public capital in the longer term, improving both potential and actual GDP [12] (p. 246).

The PNRR reforms, according to Andrea Garnero, an OECD economist, will have a direct impact on employment in terms of new hiring. They will also reduce barriers to enterprises' development and investments, increasing jobs [42].

In addition, IMF research done in 2020 demonstrates that improving upon the level of administration effectiveness can have a favorable influence on labor productivity ranging from 2 to 10% as well as leading to a 3 percent increase in production average. Thus, the study predicts that, when the reform is implemented, one-third of the difference would gradually decrease over the following ten years, resulting in a 1.5 percent increase in productivity [12] (p. 259). According to studies conducted by the Bank of Italy, the consequences of judicial reform link to the relationship between the length of trials and the economic system's output. The study demonstrates how a 15% decrease in process length between 2008 and 2016 resulted in a 0.5 percent increase in overall factor productivity. Hence, it hypothesizes that the new judicial sector reform measures will have additional impacts of the same magnitude as those mentioned, gradually and over a 5-year horizon from the time of implementation [12] (p. 260). Finally, it anticipates a one-million-job growth by 2023, compared to 2020, which saw a 767,000-job decrease owing to the pandemic. As a result, the pre-crisis situation will restore in 2023, with an active employment balance of roughly 300,000 units, which might climb to 750,000 in 2026. Female employment might increase by 350,000 units over the next six years, with an additional 90,000 employed between the ages of 15 and 29 [42]. The PNRR alone may enhance GDP by more than two percentage points during the four years 2021-24, and when combined with the budget bill, GDP can rise by up to five percentage points, marking the blueprint for Italy's stable and robust growth [7].

Nonetheless, it is crucial to recognize that Italy has a long history of volatility, economic fragility, and challenges in reforming and promoting development. Thus, if the PNRR's measures are mismanaged and wasted, Italy will have negative outcomes, finding itself worse off. Draghi stated that the public debt should rise freely because combating the health crisis without increasing public spending is impossible, otherwise, poverty and unemployment would spread uncontrollably, exacerbating Italy's already dire economic situation. Yet, the Italian debt, which is already at almost 160 percent of GDP, could reach an unsustainable level. Indeed, the ECB holds 550 billion euros out of 2,600 billion euros in Italian debt. However, if the ECB reduced the number of government bonds held on its balance sheet in response to extremely high rising inflation, the debt load would be discharged onto financial markets, making it harder for Italy to maintain it. It is important to remember that the PNRR is a plan that allocates both grants and loans and that Italy will have to repay the grants, adding to an already massive public debt. For its market credibility to recover, its growth rate must be higher than its debt rate [29]; otherwise, the country would be in an even worse economic situation than it is currently [25]. Furthermore, the Italian government must comply with the EU's investment and reform plan both effectively and coherently, since this is an essential requirement for releasing the RRF's remaining funds beginning in 2022. For a country like Italy, speed may be a double-edged sword. On the one hand, the European Union's direct influence and supervision regarding the allocation of resources can push for rapid and successful execution of the PNRR. On the other hand, the EU influence may have the opposite effect leading to the swift but erroneous, corrupted, and confusing implementation of the investments and reforms [31]. The COVID-19, with the development of the Next Generation EU and the Italian PNRR, is, nevertheless, a catalyst for a revolution in the Italian economy, bringing it out of a condition of inertia and stagnation.

Lastly, the pandemic showed the importance of coordination and solidarity among member states to maintain the stability of the Eurozone. Northern European countries such as Germany assisted nations severely impacted by the outbreak, especially Italy, by renouncing austerity and the fiscal budget regulatory ceiling. European economic interdependence created a need to solve Italian economic issues, as a recession in Southern Europe would inevitably impact Northern Europe negatively [50] (pp. 1177-1180). Thus, DI should substitute the integration-disintegration dilemma allowing heterogeneity to redistribute among member states. After 1945, the EEC saw integration as a uniform process that must be completed simultaneously and with the same speed. This conviction was expressed and continues to be expressed through the customs union, external trade policy, the EU single market, and competition policy [17] (p. 7). However, with the EEC evolving in the EU, the need for further regulations, standards, and treaties, also following the various enlargements, differentiation became a necessary principle of the new Union. As functions migrate away from the state, at different rates and in different ways [17] (pp. 5-6), it becomes crucial to recognize asymmetry in gains and costs from integration and thus increase collective actions. Still, differentiation was seen negatively and only as a temporary tool to maintain the status quo, avoiding risks and uncertainty.

Nonetheless, the pandemic highlighted how uncertainty and risks might be external and asymmetric. The Union must use differentiation as a tool of political management due to the growing diversity of interests, identities, and discourses, the rising differences in economic structures and geostrategic positions, and the contract in the resources on which states can draw [17] (p. 11).

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